

A Lightweight Federated Learning Framework for Wearable Medical Devices in Low-Resource Settings

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Abstract

Wearable medical devices enable continuous health monitoring by collecting physiological signals such as heart rate, electrocardiogram (ECG), and physical activity data. Despite their growing adoption, deploying machine learning models for healthcare remains challenging in low-resource settings such as rural clinics and community health centers due to limited computational power, constrained battery capacity, intermittent network connectivity, and strict privacy requirements regarding sensitive medical data. Standard Federated Learning (FL) enables privacy-preserving distributed learning [1], but typically assumes stable networks and resource-rich clients. To address this, we propose a lightweight, system-aware federated learning framework specifically designed for wearable health monitoring in resource-limited environments. Our approach utilizes a hierarchical architecture where edge devices aggregate data from wearables to train compact 1D-Convolutional Neural Networks (1D-CNNs). We introduce adaptive client participation and model update quantization to minimize bandwidth usage. This framework aims to enable robust, privacy-preserving cardiac monitoring and activity recognition in resource-constrained environments.

1 Introduction

Wearable medical sensors are essential for early health risk detection, yet transmitting sensitive raw data to a central cloud raises privacy concerns and demands high bandwidth. Federated Learning (FL) addresses these issues by keeping data localized and sharing only model updates [2]. However, applying FL in rural or developing regions is difficult due to “straggler” devices, unstable internet, and limited energy. As highlighted by [3], the future of digital health depends on overcoming these infrastructure barriers. Our work proposes a solution tailored to these constraints, bridging the gap between theoretical FL and real-world deployment challenges [4].

2 Proposed Framework and Methodology

As illustrated in Figure 1, our framework adopts a three-layer architecture: (1) Wearable Devices, (2) Edge Nodes (Gateways/Smartphones), and (3) the Cloud Server. In this hierarchical model, wearables operate strictly as data acquisition units to conserve battery, transmitting raw physiological signals to a nearby edge device. The edge device functions as the local training node.

Figure

Figure 1:

(a) Overview of wearable-based health monitoring in low-resource environments.

(b) Architecture of the proposed lightweight federated learning framework for wearable medical devices.

To ensure suitability for constrained environments, the framework incorporates the following lightweight mechanisms:

- **Compact Neural Network Architecture:** We utilize a lightweight 1D-Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN) tailored for physiological time-series data. Unlike heavy 2D-CNNs used in image processing, this architecture uses depth-wise separable convolutions to extract features from signals (e.g., ECG, PPG) with minimal memory footprint, preventing overfitting on limited local data through dropout and L2 regularization.
- **Reduced Synchronization Frequency:** Unlike standard FL, which aggregates frequently, our framework allows edge devices to perform multiple local training epochs before synchronization. While this slightly slows global convergence, it drastically reduces communication overhead, the primary energy consumer in wireless setups.
- **Communication Efficiency via Quantization:** To reduce transmission latency, we apply scalar quantization to model updates (gradients), compressing parameters from 32-bit floating-point to 8-bit integers. As demonstrated by [5], this technique significantly lowers bandwidth

usage without degrading the model’s convergence accuracy and ability to classify distinct physiological signals. Crucially, this quantization applies only to the model weights during transmission, not the raw physiological signals, ensuring the medical data retains its original resolution.

- **Bandwidth-Aware Scheduling and Adaptive Participation:** To address intermittent connectivity, an adaptive client participation mechanism monitors the edge device’s battery level and network bandwidth. Devices below a critical energy threshold or with unstable connections are temporarily excluded from training rounds to prevent system failure.

3 Deployment in Rural Clinical Settings

In a rural clinic scenario, a single edge device (e.g., a nurse’s tablet) may aggregate data from multiple patients’ wearables. This presents a unique advantage: the edge device trains on a “local cohort” rather than a single individual. This local aggregation helps normalize baseline shifts and reduces the drift often seen in single-user models. By averaging gradients from the local cohort before interacting with the global cloud model, the framework ensures that the global model remains generalized while being robust to individual patient outliers.

4 Implementation and Expected Outcomes

We are currently implementing the proposed architecture using the Flower federated learning framework [6], selected for its compatibility with Android and embedded Linux environments. The system will be evaluated using public health datasets, specifically the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database for cardiac anomaly detection and the PAMAP2 dataset for physical activity monitoring.

We project the following outcomes based on theoretical constraints:

1. **Communication Cost:** By applying 8-bit quantization and reducing synchronization frequency, we expect to reduce the communication payload by approximately 40% per round compared to standard Federated Averaging (FedAvg).
2. **Model Accuracy:** We expect the compact 1D-CNN to maintain accuracy within 2% of centralized baselines, as its architecture is optimized for time-series feature extraction and remains robust against noise introduced by model quantization.
3. **Robustness:** The adaptive and bandwidth-aware scheduling mechanisms are designed to maintain training stability and prevent system failure even with client dropout rates as high as 30% due to network instability or total connectivity loss.

This study contributes to the development of inclusive and scalable healthcare AI by addressing the gap between federated learning theory and real-world wearable deployment constraints. The proposed framework provides a foundation for future research on energy-efficient, secure, and adaptive federated learning systems for medical wearables and other physical AI applications. Future work is going to extend this framework through extensive simulations, real-device experimentation, and integration with multi-modal wearable sensors to support advanced health monitoring and well-being applications.

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